

Banjara women's livelihood and the revival programs of organizations in Telangana

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Abstract:

Background: Clothing is a medium to know about people, culture of the community and their region. India is full of different tribal communities where, women transfer their stories, beliefs and myths of the tribe on to the clothing with their creativity. When this mirror of the community is endangered, for any reason, society should come in to preserve it. That is what is happening with the traditional craft of Banjaras. The colorful and picturesque Banjara costume and ornamentation identifying the tribe was endangered for many reasons. They started to discard their age old traditional costume and adopted local dress patterns putting the existence of the craft into danger. The study has focused to understand and document how the organizations both government and non-government in Telangana have come forward to preserve this craft with their programs and how the livelihood of the tribal women in Telangana has changed due to this intervention of the organizations.

Keywords: Banjara Embroidery, Livelihood of Banjara Women, Revival Programs

Introduction:

The Banjaras are nomadic tribes who were believed to have migrated from Afghanistan, before settling in Rajasthan and other parts of India. They were wanderers and used to transport food grains on bullocks under different rulers in India like Maratha rulers of Satara, Peshwas of Pune, Nijam of Hyderabad etc. They settled in different districts of Telangana, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Tamilnadu etc. It was this limitlessness and freedom that is reflected through the Banjara embroidery designs. Banjara embroidery is a combination of colorful threads, design patters, mirror work, stitching patterns, appliqué or patch work. It consists of the intricate thread work making geometrical patterns with countless of stitching skills. This traditional craft is inherited from their fore fathers and has been passed on from generation to generation.

As they started to settle in different regions in India, some got into agriculture and others into labour work in the cities and towns. Banjaras are more significant and prominent in number in Telangana. With the change in time they have tried to adjust with society resulting in a detachment from their traditions and culture. One of them is, slow vanishing of their traditional needle craft and in turn losing their ethnic identity.

Some NGOs and Govt. organizations in different states have come forward to help artisans

to retain this traditional Banjara art. For example, Sandur Kushala Kendra in Karnataka (SKKK) is a non-profit organization in Bellary district promoting craft-based livelihood; in Tamilnadu, under craft initiative of THI, some older women were trained in the craft in turn others joined and formed a craft association called as "Porgai"; and Craft Council of Telangana is working towards helping artisans and promoting tribal art form with their many programs including workshops, training programs and other financially supported initiations.

This study is focused to understand and document such support systems, their interventions and programs they conducted that helped artisans of this traditional craft to sustain. This study also focuses on understanding the impact of it on the Banjara women's livelihood and financial freedom.

Thus the current study has been planned with the following objectives:

1. To document the embroidery of Banjara community with respect to technique, material, color, designs, and motifs used in it, before and during the intervention.
2. To collect and document different programs of organization's to revive the craft for sustainability of Banjara embroidery.
3. To study and document the impact of the organization's intervention on livelihood of Banjara women and their financial freedom.

Method of Data Collection:

Since my study demands descriptive approach and needs a proper documentation, I will embrace qualitative method to analyze data collected through a survey method. My primary data source are in-depth interviews with the artisans and organizers of at the agency and individual artisans of different thandas using structured and unstructured questionnaires, mails and phone calls and my secondary data sources are the newspaper articles, articles in the digital media, printed information from the agencies, web sources and books etc. This study aims to understand the impact of intervention of organizations to revive the craft on the livelihood of Banjara women in Telangana.

Area of study:

The Telangana state has 33 districts and almost all the districts have population of Banjara communities settled in them. Villages are selected for the study that have been chosen by the organizations for the revival.

Sample selection:

Artisans: A sample size of 50-60 Banjara women were chosen from Telangana. The sample size included Banjara women who have been practicing the needle craft and in the age range of 25-75 years from different regions of Telangana.

Organizations: Couple of organizations that have been supporting Banjara craft since 20-25 years in and around Hyderabad to preserve the craft. Particularly, Crafts Council of Telangana, Tribal Welfare Department and Nehru Centenary Tribal Museum.

Individuals: People from fashion field like boutique owners, craft stores owners, students of NIFT (National Institute of Fashion Technology, Hyderabad) and individual customers.

Data collection:

Results and Discussions:

Data about the traditional art of Banjara needle craft was obtained through textual sources and field study. The primary data was collected from conducting in-depth interviews with artisans of different thandas (tribal hamlets) in Telangana, employees of government and non-government organizations and other people associated with this craft. The secondary data sources include books, digital articles, museums, craft stores, and personal photo albums of the artisans etc. Data acquired from artisans of different Banjara thandas, Shilparamam, scholars, artists, shops, thandas of different villages.

Banjara Thandas visited for data collection:

- Yellamma Thanda, Ibrahimpatnam, Ranga Reddy Dist, Telangana
- Lambadi Thanda, Wanaparthi, Telanagana
- Perkiweedu Thanda, Mahboobnagar, Telangana
- Maktha Venkatapur Thanda, Parigi, Vikarabad Dist, Telangana
- Roopla Thanda, Shivampet, Medak, Telangana
- Mantralamma Thanda, Devarakonda, Telangana
- Kotha Thanda, Dindi, Nalgonda Dist, Telangana

Organizations and individuals:

- Scholars and individual artists related to Banjara tribe
- Tribal welfare department (Banjara Bhavan), Hyderabad
- Crafts Council of Telangana (CCT), Banjara hills, Hyderabad
- Nehru Centenary Tribal Salarjung Museum, Masab tank, Hyderabad
- Shilparamam, Madhapur, Hyderabad
- Craft Stores of Santhosh nagar, Koti etc in Hyderabad

Traditionally this craft is a community specific art and is a knowledge passed from generations to generations by word of mouth and involving in the activity from childhood. Banjara women do it for themselves and their family members. Due to many changes in the lifestyle, this traditional art started to lose its charm. Some of the reasons came across during the discussions were:

For economic reasons, Banjara women started to involve into different works outside the house like, agriculture and labor works so the production of the art reduced to minimum.

When these women started to go out, their traditional attire was not preferred because of the societal acceptance and ease. Banjara clothing is a beautiful work of art with all the embroidery and different materials like cowries, shells, coins etc but for the same reasons, their attire is heavy to carry which reduced the preference.

These and other reasons made their ancient beliefs and practices to go through radical reduction and less preferred. Now the usage of their art and costume reduced to mere occasions like festivals and

marriages.

Organizations and their Intervention:

Some government and non-government organizations in different states of India have come forward to help artisans to retain this beautiful tribal. They are working towards retaining the art with their different programs that encourage artisans to create more and spread this art to more people.

While researching about this art, I found some organizations, nation-wide, are working remarkably to help the artisans to continue working in all scenarios. This support is resulting not only to sustain the art but also making Banjara women to earn their livelihood and to be financially independent.

Let me discuss about the organizations working for this art.

Craft Council of Telangana, Banjara Hills, Hyderabad, Telangana:

Under Crafts Council of India, CCT, Crafts Council of Telangana is working towards helping artisans and promoting tribal art forms by conducting different programs.

Crafts Council of Telangana aims to uplift artisans. The CCT has been playing a major role in promoting these crafts by organising multiple exhibitions and workshops along with handholding the artisans and continues to influence the life of the artisans from the State. The voluntary and not-for-profit organization came into being in 1987 in the undivided Andhra Pradesh and was inspired by the work of Kamaladevi Chattopadhyay who started the Crafts Council of India in the 1960s. Started off with a 15-member team in the 1980s, the council has over 170 members including artisans and has held many sessions with the craftsmen even during pandemic.

"It became a big challenge for us to convince them

to mould their art. We conducted workshops for a year and were able to train 150-160 members and now many are selling their designs in national and international markets," Khemka said.

Tribal Welfare Department, Banjara Bhavan, Hyderabad:

Several Banjara Bhavan was built by the government of Telangana for Banjara community's betterment. Tribal leaders and intellectuals of the

tribe are conducting number of programs by making it a platform for the uplift and development of the community. Part of it, they have a permanent store established for the Banjara tribal art and craft along with frequent exhibitions of their craft.

Nehru Centenary Tribal Museum, Masa Tank, Hyderabad:

The Nehru Centenary Tribal Museum displays the rich tribal cultural heritage of Andhra and Telangana. Located in the premises of the Telugu Samkshema Bhavan, the Nehru Centenary Tribal Museum (NCTM) is dedicated to the social and cultural life of tribal communities in Telangana and Andhra Pradesh. It has galleries for displaying artefacts related to tribal communities from different districts and a mini auditorium that screens films on tribal culture and development and a library with over 14,500 books on tribal communities from India and around the world.

Revival Programs of the Organizations;

Each organization is working towards the uplift and conservation of Banjara tribal art by designing number of different programs for the same cause. There are some programs like conducting training and exhibitions that are common but there are many contemporary approaches and methods they adopted to maximize the benefit of the artisans. For decades these organizations have been helping the artisans not only providing financial assistance but also by training

them to be self-sustaining even after these programs.

Here I am discussing the revival programs and approaches that organizations adopted in conserving Banjara tribal art and in turn helped the artisans, particularly the Banjara women to be financially independent by making the art as their livelihood.

Exhibitions:

From centuries, Banjara women have been stitching embroidery only for their personal use, for themselves and their family. With change in time, to adopt the societal scenario, for comfort, and for other reasons, they started to shift from wearing their traditional attire to contemporary clothes. Government organizations saw it as declination of the traditional art form and came up with different strategies, one of them is conducting exhibitions.

Initially the organizations provided financial aid to the artisans so that they produce their traditional art and exhibit in Hyderabad. Later, artisans were encouraged to do their art on different products like pillow covers, pouches, bed sheets, saree blouse, fabric belts, bags etc. These products were liked and purchased by people, including non-Banjara population that boosted the artisans to create more.

Trainings and Workshops:

Banjara women acquire the skill of embroidery from their ancestors. Organizations planned for exposure of this craft to more people and started conducting workshops for interested Banjara women. It was like training more and more people to learn and produce this craft. Workshops were arranged in Hyderabad by calling Banjara women from different districts of Telangana (and

Andhra Pradesh before the state division)

Senior Banjara women were selected from selected districts and made them train the younger women of this craft. Products produced in the workshops were sold in the exhibitions conducted later. Senior women were benefitted by the payment and younger women by learning the craft. Trained women were given work to go back and produce in the comfort of their homes.

Angadi, the Craft Bazaar:

Angadi is a craft bazaar which is an initiation of Crafts Council of Telangana that showcases talents of craftsman from all over India. Craftsmen including Banjara women from different districts come and participate with their products. It is like other exhibitions but there is no prior funding

from the organizations rather they create with their own finances and sale in the Angadi for profit. Angadi is arranged for 3-4 days in a row in the spaces of CCT in regular intervals where not only Banjara but all other crafts are encouraged.

Sales at Gated Communities:

Exhibitions were arranged in the gated communities of Hyderabad where high society people would be interested to acquire these products as traditional souvenirs and some people would give commercial orders to do the embroidery of their choice on their clothes raising the income of these

artisans. When these exhibitions were conducted, artisans sold many of their products and got income and encouragement to do more work. Angoori of Devarakonda recollects how these exhibitions gave her the freedom from labour work and raised respect in the society as an artisan along with financial benefits.

Meetings with potential clientele/advisers:

Organization arrange meeting of artisans with different people like boutique owners, freelance designers, fashion institutes etc. where the artisans learn many useful things that are important for their development.

Sessions teach them:

- How to improve their skills to make embroidered textiles more attractive in less time?
- How to adapt to new requirements of the customers to handle the orders?
- Creating new forms and items according to the market requirements
- How to form groups of artisans and work together in their hamlets?
- How to do online sales of their items?

Online marketing:

Organizations took the artisans products to online and helped them with the required knowledge of online market, like taking pictures of their products, uploading the images to websites, how to catalogue them, pricing their works, handling the orders, payment apps and money transactions, and helped them with write-ups etc. Professional from the industry were invited to conduct sessions to teach the artisans the tips and tricks to update themselves with the technology. Some of them are now well versed with the techniques and also helping the younger groups. Crafts Council of Telangana has its Instagram handle @craftscounciloft where information about their programs and products are continuously publicised for public information.

Artisan showing me box full of her creations ready to go online along with different stitches she uses She was one of the earlier batch trainees who is now

capable of creating customised products, handling online sales and also training younger women on a regular basis.

"I and my team do not compromise with the quality of work we do, so we get orders regularly. I managed to marry off my daughter with my income without talking any help from my husband" says laughs Anasuya proudly.

Owning commercial stores:

Now after many years of support and experience, artisans have started their own commercial stores in the city, making them proud owners of a business. There are many stores of the artisans in Santhoshnagar, Koti, Madhapur, Saroornagar, Hubsiguda etc in the city (Hyderabad). They get the products done in the villages and selling them in the city which in turn is providing source of income to those who are back in villages. This initiation of the organization helped them to earn for their family and even their second generation family members are showing interest in the art.

Teaching in Schools:

Due to the revival programs of these organizations, exposure to this traditional art has increased and people's interest increased. Some schools in Hyderabad decided to conduct classes for their students as part of their extra-curricular activities, for example, Akshaya School in Banjara Hills and Nachiketa School in Madhapur. They invited senior Banjara women to come and take classes for their students on a regular basis. This became an opportunity to earn more for some of

Awards:

These interventions of the organizations not only made Banjara women of Telangana financially independent but also won them awards for their work and contribution. They are appreciated and awarded state awards and UNESCO awards for their contribution. Angoori Sepavat of Hyderabad is one such example of a recognised and award-winning craftsperson who has held demos of her work at crafts-promotion events. She is honoured by Crafts

these women. Their travelling expenses and teaching time is well paid off by the school management. Not only financial benefit, it is also like a confidence booster and encouragement for these women to continue their traditional art.

Collaborations:

Revival programs by both government and non-government organizations proved beneficial to Banjara art. As mentioned earlier, these revival programs were organised in other states too. Though their programs worked individually, there are collaborations too. That is, Banjara artisans of different states were encouraged equally by conducting exhibitions in collaborations where artisans of different states and organizations were allowed to participate and sell their products in other states too, increasing their chances of earning. Also these collaborations made the women cross borders and establish contacts across states. Along with financial opportunities, confidence levels clearly increased. Now they communicate and work across border which is positive for the sustainment of the art.

Council of Telangana for her role in spreading Banjara needle craft. Kethavath Laxmi Bai, is one of the early artisans who were invited to train other women under the revival programs. She is still sticking to the tedious but traditional techniques of the craft and escaping to non-traditional the short cuts of the business. After years of working with the organizations, she is currently providing employment to about 200 women belonging to her

community in her own village, Yellamma Thanda. After three decades of adapting to changing times, the Banjara women led by Laxmi are embroidering

The Kamala Samman Award of The Crafts Council of India is the highest among the Kamala Awards. It recognises and honours a senior person whose long and dedicated work in the field has

blouses, cushion covers, cell phone covers, dupattas and sarees in their traditional style, applying it to contemporary trends and needs.

significantly benefitted craft communities and transformed their lives. Smt Lakshmi proudly showing her products; Customised items that are ready to be dispatched her clients in different places.

"I lost my husband very early but managed to lead my life decently. Unfortunately I lost my grown up son recently, his widow and 2 years old son are my responsibility now. I am thankful to the revival programs because of which, my traditional craft is serving as back support for my life's challenges." says wet-eyed Laxmi Bai.

Another artisan, Smt. Anasuya of Ibrahimpatnam,

who is honoured for her contribution proudly shows her house that she built on her own with after starting to sell her work to boutiques in Hyderabad, exhibit with artisans of Sandur Kushal Kendra of Karnataka and take classes in the schools etc. she is teaching the craft in her village to younger women of her community.

Smt Anasuya showing me her collection for the upcoming exhibition in Delhi.

Conclusion:

Banjara needle craft is an integral part of the cultural heritage of Banjara community in Telangana, deeply rooted in the traditions and identity of the Banjara community. When this craft was endangered, successful attempts to preserve, promote, and sustain this traditional craft was carried out by different organizations. Their timely projects and efforts to revive this traditional craft not only helped the art but also helping the artisans to be independent and confident with new exposure and financial independence, in turn, preserving and

extending the culture heritage of the community. With the improved knowledge and skills, artisans attempting to experimentation of the craft without losing the traditional essence is appreciable. I am glad to work on this project because of which I could meet all these artisans and organizations and understand how their efforts turned fruitful in saving this communal craft along with economic development of the artisans.

Selfie with the winner of Kamala Sanman Award, Smt. Lakshmi Bai of Yellamma Thanda

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